

Supporting Information for:

**Roll-to-roll mechanical exfoliation for large-area van der Waals films
with preserved crystallographic alignment**

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Figure S1. Evolution of in-plane anisotropy with the number of BP bulk crystals, intentionally misaligned, in the roll-to-roll film. (a–d) For films produced by exfoliating 1, 2, 3, and 4 BP bulk crystals intentionally misaligned (left: roller setup photograph; middle: optical image, right: polar plot of normalized transmitted intensity vs. polarization angle). With one crystal (a) the film shows a single, well-defined optical axis (strong dichroism). Adding a second crystal (b) with a different in-plane orientation introduces a second preferred direction and even further angular dispersion induced during the rolling process. With three crystals (c) the polar plot exhibits three competing anisotropic directions, and with four crystals (d) there are no clear directions and the film has lost its anisotropy.

Figure S2. AFM morphology and flake statistics of a BP film on SiO₂/Si. (a) AFM height map of the roll-to-roll-exfoliated BP film. Flakes have been removed from the SiO₂ surface at the right size by scanning a diamond record vinyl stylus to ensure a region with bare substrate to perform the thickness analysis. Special care has been taken to avoid registering the thickness of overlapping flakes. (b) Scatter plot of thickness vs. lateral length extracted for 133 flakes in the scanned area; marginal histograms (top/right) show the distributions of length and thickness, respectively.

Figure S3. Areal coverage analysis of BP films by image masking. (a) Optical image of the BP film. (b) Binary mask built in Gwyddion highlighting uncovered regions (red overlay) on the grayscale image (c) Histogram of coverage extracted from 32 images with a Gaussian fit (dashed line). The distribution yields an average coverage of $\approx 93.9\%$ with $\sigma \approx 3.4\%$, indicating highly uniform, near-continuous films.

Figure S4. Atomic resolution STEM-ADF imaging and TEM diffraction over multiple Black Phosphorus flakes. (a) Optical image of roll-to-roll mechanically exfoliated black phosphorus transferred on to a Si_3N_4 TEM membrane grid. 1-4 indicate the explored flakes. (b-e) Atomic resolution STEM-ADF images of flakes 1-4, respectively, observed along the [010] zone axis. (f-i) Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns of flakes 1-4, respectively. SAED provides a diffraction pattern averaged over a large area (several microns) of the flake, demonstrating the consistency of the crystallinity of the exfoliated flakes.

Figure S5. Set-up for Dichroism Measurements. The custom-built setup is integrated into a Motic BA 310 MET microscope. A polarizer, mounted on a rotator, is positioned between the light source and the anisotropic film under analysis. By adjusting the microscope's XY stage, different regions of the film can be examined. The intensity variations are extracted using the microscope lenses, enabling precise characterization of the film's anisotropic optical properties.

Figure S6. Comparison between dichroism measurements and SAED patterns of a black phosphorus flake. An exemplary comparison of several selected flakes in which SAED analysis was performed, followed by dichroism measurements on the same TEM grid. This approach allows for a direct correlation between the structural information obtained from SAED and the optical dichroism observed in each flake in this case it shows the primary 30 degree orientation of the flakes in the grid.

Figure S7. Comparison between dichroism measurements and SAED patterns of a black phosphorus flake. An exemplary comparison of several selected flakes in which SAED analysis was performed, followed by dichroism measurements on the same TEM grid. This approach allows for a direct correlation between the structural information obtained from SAED and the optical dichroism observed in each flake in this case it shows the primary 0 degree orientation of the flakes in the grid.

Figure S8. Different anisotropic materials films. Following the same procedure describe in the figure 1 we tried different anisotropic materials to check if the technique was reproducible for different crystals. A linear dichroism was done to check the films. The scalebars in the figures correspond to 0.5 cm and the scale bar in the inset is 20 μm .

Figure S9. Flake-size statistics for layered materials exfoliated by roll-to-roll. (a–c, top) Scatter plots of width vs. length for 200 flakes per material, with marginal histograms (top/right. Materials: (a) GeS, (b) MoO₃, (c) CrSBr. The lower panels show optical image of each film region. All three materials show a high in-plane anisotropy with large lengths and narrow widths allowing one to extract this statistics out of optical image analysis.

Figure S10. Polar intensity maps and orientation histograms over a centimeter-scale region. (a) Polar plots of transmittance intensity for each zone along the tape, as defined in Fig. 4. (b) Histograms of the preferred direction (zigzag axis) for each zone (colored as in Figure 4 of the main text).

Figure S11. Anisotropy retention of BP films under bending.(a) A polycarbonate (PC) substrate with a BP film (panel b) is first analyzed in the flat state. (c) Dichroism measurements are performed, confirming the anisotropic alignment of the flakes. (d) The substrate is then bent 20 times (with a curvature radius ~ 1.4 cm) to test the mechanical robustness of the BP film (panel e) and evaluate possible degradation of anisotropy. (f) After the repeated bending, dichroism measurements are carried out again, showing no significant changes, thus demonstrating that the BP film retains its directional optical response. Small angle misalignment is attributed to the error re-mounting the sample under the optical microscope after the bending test.

Lithography procedure

For the fabrication of the electrode array we used the SmartPrint lithography machine and the double resist fabrication process. We first spin coat LOR2A at 3k rpm for 40s, we bake the substrate at 180 °C for 3 min. Afterwards, we spin coat the second layer of AZ1505 positive resist at 4k rpm for 40 sec and bake at 100°C for 1 min. Subsequently, we expose our pre-designed electrode pattern for 0.6 s with the 10X objective of the microscope. Now that the resist is cured we develop with the AZ726 MIF developer by submerging the sample for 19 sec and rinse with DI water. We are left with our desired pattern ready for the thermal evaporator.

Figure S12. Picture of the pattern after developing. After developing we are left with the desired pattern (a) where the gold will be placed in the evaporator (b) and our electrodes will be fabricated to afterwards place the film on top (c).

Figure S13. More devices where fabricated to check conductivity properties and reproducibility. We can observe that from the same BP film used for the fabrication of the describe device in the paper we can obtain devices which match its electrical behavior.

Figure S14. I–V curve of anisotropic BP device shown in Figure 6 of main text. An intensity-versus-voltage graph is included to illustrate the differences between regions where the device exhibits higher and lower currents. The voltage sweep was performed from 0 to 1 V.

Figure S15. Angle-resolved IV curves in black phosphorus (BP) devices. IV measurements for five independent devices (Device 1–5) over 0–1 V. Each panel shows series acquired while measuring the sample current from 0° to 360° in 45° steps. Measurement conditions and procedure are those used for the devices shown on Fig. S12.

Figure S16. Anisotropic Conductivity Analysis of CrSBr Films. (a, top left) Device featuring eight gold electrodes arranged in a circular pattern on a SiO₂ substrate, separated by 45° and converging toward a central 60 μm diameter circle without contact. (a, bottom right) Image of the bottom half of the device after transferring a CrSBr film, connecting the electrodes. (b) Polar plot of the ribbons angle comparing in respect to the horizontal axis, identifying the armchair orientation of the CrSBr film after transferring on top of the electrodes. Thanks to the inset which shows a magnification of the film we can observe the orientation of the ribbons (d) Polar plot of current measured at 1 V for different pairs of drain-source electrodes forming different angles. The peanut-shaped pattern in the current plot corresponds well to the anisotropic transmittance, confirming higher conductivity along the armchair direction.

To demonstrate the potential of our roll-to-roll exfoliated anisotropic films for optoelectronic applications, we fabricated a proof-of-concept polarization-sensitive photodetector based on CrSBr on a polycarbonate substrate. Two sequential transfers of CrSBr films were transferred on top of each other to ensure an improved percolation in the film. During transfer we ensure that in both transfers the tape angles are kept aligned. The crystallographic alignment of the flakes was determined directly from reflection-mode optical microscopy, as the ribbon-like morphology of CrSBr enables easy identification of the dominant crystallographic direction a-axis.

The metal contacts were deposited by thermal evaporation of Cr (5 nm) / Au (50 nm) through a shadow mask, with the electrodes intentionally patterned at approximately 45° with respect to the flake alignment. This geometry ensures that the photocurrent anisotropy is not dominated by the electrode layout. Indeed, the polarization-dependent photoresponse shown in Figure S16 exhibits a clear sinusoidal dependence, with maxima

aligned with the crystallographic a-axis of the CrSBr flakes. The electrode orientation is indicated by vertical blue lines, and the crystal orientation by red lines, confirming that the polarization sensitivity originates from the intrinsic anisotropy of the film.

While this device is intended as a proof of concept and has not been fully optimized, it clearly demonstrates the feasibility of integrating the exfoliated films into polarization-sensitive optoelectronic devices.

Figure S17. Role of the electrode orientation in the polarization-dependent photoresponse of roll-to-roll devices.

(a) Polarization dependence of photocurrent while applying source-drain voltage of 1V, an exposing the entire device to homogeneous illumination with wavelength $\lambda = 550 \text{ nm}$ and a power density $P = 31 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$. Blue (red) vertical lines indicate polarization along the electrode edges (b-axis of the CrSBr flakes). The black line is a fitting of the experimental datapoints to a cosine function. (b) Same as (a) for $\lambda = 650 \text{ nm}$ and $P = 57 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$ (c) Microscope image of the device. The electrodes are 1 mm wide. Blue and red lines correspond to the polarization directions indicated (a) and (b). (d) Zoom-in of the area indicated by a white square in (c), showing the orientation of the crystalline flakes.